

DEVELOPMENT OF HIGH PERFORMANCE CARBON/CARBON BRAKE DISK FOR AN ADVANCED AIRCRAFT

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SUMMARY: This paper describes the manufacturing process and the dynamic torque test result of carbon/carbon aircraft brake disk. Through the methods of a pitch impregnation and chemical vapor infiltration using specially designed preform carbon/carbon brake disk with required properties such as friction and wear, density, thermal and mechanical properties etc. have been manufactured for the qualification test after the processes of a nondestructive test, a machining, a metal channel installation and an antioxidation treatment. All qualification tests including a dynamic torque test and a service life test were performed according to the specifications of the MIL-W-5013 and the GD16ZL001B of the Lockheed(General Dynamics) with an inertia dynamometer. From the all qualification test the brake assembly has shown superior braking performance comparing with the current qualified carbon/carbon brake disk and has passed the all requirements.

KEYWORDS: carbon/carbon brake disk, dynamic torque test, inertia dynamometer, MIL-W-5013,

INTRODUCTION

Because of their low density, excellent high temperature mechanical properties, self-lubricative and high heat absorption capability, carbon/carbon composites have been considered one of the best materials in the aircraft brake industry. Although aircraft brake is a core of the landing part, large consumed and connected directly with the safety of a pilot only several countries have succeed in developing carbon/carbon brake disk in the worldwide.

In partnership with the Daewoo Heavy Industries Ltd. We, the Agency for Defense Development have been developing carbon/carbon brake disk. In the brake disk development it is necessary to test and evaluate dynamic torque property of the brake materials using an inertia dynamometer. In accordance with the specifications of MIL-W-5013 and the GD16ZL001B of the General Dynamics (Lockheed) regarding the development of aircraft brake disk we have performed dynamic torque test consisting of 45 stops of landplane landing design gross weight, 5 stops of maximum landing design gross weight and 1 stop of maximum design gross weight(rejected take-off) for several sets of brake assembly. In addition to the test, a service life test of 500 stops under the purpose of evaluating service life and reliability of brake disk has been performed. All results from these tests have satisfied the requirements.

FABRICATION OF CARBON/CARBON BRAKE DISK

Carbon/carbon brake disks were manufactured using a typical process of liquid impregnation and carbonization. In the fabrication process PAN-based carbon fiber and coal-tar pitch were used as a reinforcement and a matrix precursor respectively. To obtain a good friction property and structural stability high modulus chopped carbon fiber after undergone heat-treated at about 2500 was used for friction surface and continuous carbon fiber fabric consisted of a center part of brake disk which plays important role in load-bearing during operation. The properties of carbon fiber and pitch used are in table 1 and 2 respectively.

Table 1: Property of carbon fiber used in the manufacturing carbon/carbon brake disk

Tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Elongation (%)	Density (g/cc)	Filament diameter (μm)	Specific heat (kJ/kg.K)
3,400	235	1.3	1.8	6.8	0.17

Table 2: Property of coal-tar pitch used a matrix precursor

Specific Gravity	Softening Point ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Carbon Yield, 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (%)	Toluene insoluble (wt%)	d002(\AA)
1.31	117	43.0	41.0	3.581

As the first step in the fabrication, green disks were manufactured using a pitch-prepreg and chopped carbon fiber with a hydraulic press and the green disk was carbonized using a furnace in a special metal container designed to suppress the green disk expanding in carbonization and then several times of impregnation and carbonization processes were performed to obtain a required density. In the middle of the densification process 2 or 3 times of a high temperature heat treatment called a graphitization were applied to facilitate a pitch impregnation and develop a matrix microstructure having a good friction property. After the liquid densification process the brake disk with a required density was suffered a chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) as a final densification. The brake disks having a enough density were evaluated by non-destructive test (NDT) an internal flaws and prepared the dynamic torque test through the processes of machining according to a drawing, metal channel installation and antioxidation coating at non-friction parts. Table 3 shows typical properties of the carbon/carbon brake disk.

DYNAMIC TORQUE TEST

Introduction

According to the specifications of the MIL-W-5013 regarding only a military aircraft development and the GD16ZL001B of General Dynamics(Lockheed), a dynamic torque test is should be performed for development of an aircraft brake with 45 stops of a landplane landing design gross weight braking, 5 stops of maximum landing gross weight braking and 1 stop of rejected take-off(RTO) similar to an aircraft maximum design gross weight. All tests

should be performed using a same brake disk assembly but RTO test can be performed using tested assembly or a new one.

Table 3: Typical properties of the carbon/carbon brake disk

Density (g/cc)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Compressive strength (MPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	ILSS (MPa)	Thermal conductivity (W/m.K)
>1.75	80-110	110-140	100-140	10-12	25-30(∥) 80-90(⊥)

After the dynamic torque test, service life dynamic torque test which is consisted of 333 stops of landplane landing design gross weight braking and 167 stops of 74% landplane landing design gross weight braking should be performed to evaluate braking reliability and service life in accordance with the GD16ZL001B.

Figure 1: Photograph of the prototype brake assembly

Braking Performance Test

Test and Evaluation Criteria

All dynamic torque tests were performed according to the MIL-W-5013 and GD16ZL001B using a certified inertia dynamometer which can simulate kinetic energy absorbed by a brake assembly in an aircraft landing and evaluated by criteria such as a maximum braking pressure, braking stability, braking distance, tire bead and wheel temperature defined in Table 4 and Table 5 respectively. For our development program the dynamic torque tests were performed for an existing qualified disk assembly and the prototype brake disk assembly under the purpose of comparing braking performance. Figure 1 shows the prototype brake disk assembly.

Test Results

Table 6 and 7 show the dynamic torque test results for the prototype and an existing qualified carbon/carbon brake disk assembly. Considering the braking pressure needed to satisfy braking distance requirement an existing brake assembly need more braking pressure than the prototype brake assembly. It can be concluded that a prototype assembly has better braking performance than a qualified existing brake assembly in conditions of the landplane landing design gross weight braking and the maximum landing design gross weight braking. Especially in the RTO test the prototype showed superior braking performance that only as low as pressure of 1176 psi is necessary to stop an aircraft safely within a required braking distance. From the RTO result it is evaluated the prototype has more survivability in emergency landing which is being issued in a qualified current brake assembly.

Table 4: Dynamic torque test conditions

Test Conditions	A	B	C
Aircraft weight (pounds)	19,500	27,500	37,500
Braking kinetic energy (million feet pounds)	5.7	10.5	18.1
Inertia equivalent weight of dynamometer (pounds, max)	9,536	12,650	13,191
Braking velocity (knots min.)	116	137	176
Tire load (pounds)	7,380	10,147	13,811
Tire rolling radius (inches)	11.7	11.4	11.3

A : Landplane landing design gross weight braking test

B : Maximum landing gross weight braking test

C : Maximum design gross weight braking test(Rejected take-off test)

Table 5: Evaluation criteria in the dynamic torque test

Test conditions		A	B	C
Requirement				
Max. allowable braking pressure (psi)		2,300	2,300	2,300
Braking distance (feet)		2,238	3,108	5,250
Tire bead seat temperature (max. F)		400	400	410
Axle temperature (max. F)	Inboard	450	450	900
	Outboard	400	400	
Fuse plug release		No	No	After 1 min.

Table 6: Test result of 45 stops in landplane landing design gross weight

Items	Requirements	Existing brake	Results
Braking pressure (psi)	2,300 (max.)	959	506
Braking torque (in.lbs)	NA	29,494	33,286
Deceleration rate (ft/sec ²)	8.60	8.47	9.17
Braking distance (feet)	2,238	2,251	2,136
Braking temperature (°C)	NA	500-700	600-700

Table 7: Test result of 5 stops in maximum landing design gross weight

Items	Requirements	Existing brake	Results
Braking pressure (psi)	2,300 (max.)	1,486	817
Braking torque (in.lbs)	NA	34,366	41,789
Deceleration rate (ft/sec ²)	8.59	9.07	8.72
Braking distance (feet)	3,108	2,872	3,103
Braking temperature (°C)	NA	800-1200	1000-1400

From the braking torque and pressure curve, a braking performance of the prototype brake assembly showed more stable than an existing brake throughout braking. Table 8 is the result of the RTO test for the prototype brake assembly. In the test several R-type thermocouples were installed on the two stator disks in order to measure friction temperature and the temperature was monitored only up to 1700 due to thermocouples melting but the real friction temperature would be estimated as high as 2000. After the test several metal channel were melted and a fuse plug released about 100 seconds elapsed after the stopping.

Table 8: Test result of rejected take-off(RTO) test

Items	Requirements	Results
Braking pressure (psi)	2,300 (max.)	1,176
Braking torque (in.lbs)	NA	41,849
Deceleration rate (ft/sec ²)	8.40	8.74
Braking distance (feet)	5,250	5,112
Braking temperature (°C)	NA	>1700

Figure 2 shows the RTO test with a burning brake assembly.

Fig. 2: Photograph showing the RTO test

RESULT OF SERVICE LIFE DYNAMIC TORQUE TEST

In accordance with the GD16ZL001B, 500 stops of service life test was performed for the prototype brake assembly. Table 9 and 10 show the service life dynamic torque test results respectively. During the service life test no brake disk failure was happened and showed superior braking performance and reliability. The service life cycle was projected more than 1000 landings.

Table 9: Test result of 333 stops of service life test in landplane landing design gross weight

Items	Requirements	Results
Braking energy (x10 ⁶ ft.lbs)	5.7	5.9
Braking pressure (psi)	2300 (max.)	542
Braking torque (in.lbs)	NA	33,432
Deceleration rate (ft/sec ²)	8.6	9.2
Braking distance (ft)	2,238	2,159
Braking temperature (°C)	NA	600-700

Table 10: Test result of 167 stop service life test in 74% landplane landing design gross weight

Items	Requirements	Result
Braking energy (x10 ⁶ ft.lbs)	4.2	4.3
Braking pressure (psi)	2300 (max.)	430
Braking torque (in.lbs)	NA	24,789
Deceleration rate (ft/sec ²)	6.4	7.0
Braking distance (ft)	2,238	2,077
Braking temperature (°C)	NA	500-600

CONCLUSIONS

In accordance with the specifications of MIL-W-5013 and GD16ZL001B dynamic torque test was performed with an inertia dynamometer for the prototype brake assembly and an existing qualified brake assembly. Comparing with an existing carbon/carbon brake disk assembly the prototype brake disk assembly showed more stable braking stability, higher braking performance due to higher friction coefficient and evaluated satisfying all the specification requirements.

500 stops of the service life test according to the GDZL001B specification was performed to evaluate a service life and braking reliability. From the test, the prototype brake assembly showed no failure and stable braking performance throughout all the test and service life was projected more than 1000 landing cycles.

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